

REVIEW ARTICLE ABOUT BLOOD PRESSURE AND ATMOSPHERIC PRESSURE

Mohamed Ahmed Neama Hamid

University of Wasit/ College of Sciences/ Department of Medical Physics

*Baneen Haitham Abed Jaafar, Hanin Hani Hamzah Rashid, Tiba Salim Habeeb Timoz,
Raghad Raied Naji Wadi*

Al_Mustaqbal University College/ Department of Applied Medical Physics

Abstract:

This research discussed pressure in general, atmospheric pressure and blood pressure, as pressure is the force acting vertically on the surface area, and blood pressure is the pressure that blood exerts on the arteries. In the second chapter, we talked about blood pressure and atmospheric pressure more broadly in terms of high and low blood pressure, mercury and digital blood pressure measuring devices, their types and components, as well as atmospheric pressure measuring devices. In this research, we have concluded that atmospheric pressure is the force exerted by air above the surface, while blood pressure is the force of blood pushing against the walls of blood vessels. It has been shown that atmospheric pressure is no different from blood pressure, as they are related to each other, as when atmospheric pressure decreases, blood pressure decreases automatically, as well as the difference in readings of electronic devices from mercury. We also found that the laboratory-made device has an accuracy closer to the standard device manufactured by a manufacturing company, and it was found that the standard deviation is 5 mm Hg for diastolic pressure and 3.7 mm Hg for systolic pressure. It was found that the deviation in this percentage does not affect the doctor's determination of whether the person whose pressure is to be measured has high blood pressure or not.

Introduction:

Pressure (symbol p) is the specific force acting vertically on a surface area. There are several types of pressure, the most famous of which are atmospheric pressure, static fluid pressure and moving fluid pressure. According to the International System of Units, pressure is expressed in pascals or N/m^2

One of the most important and common types of pressure is atmospheric pressure, which is the weight of a column of air located on an area of 1 square centimeter in a vacuum. It is equivalent to the weight of a column of mercury on the same area with a height of 760 millimeters, which can be measured using a manometer. The unit mm Hg is one of the manometric units for measuring pressure [1].

Pressure is defined as an effect that occurs when a force is applied to a surface, and pressure is symbolized by the symbol.[2] p

1 or $p=dF/(dA)$ $F/A_p=$

Pressure = the force perpendicular to the area

where p is the pressure, F is the force perpendicular, A is the area

Pressure is a standard quantity whose units in the International System of Units are the pascal Pa where

Pascal = m^2 / N^1 , and in the American Specialized System of Units the unit is psi

where $\text{psi} = 1 \text{ p} / \text{Inch}^2$ Pressure is considered one of the basic coordinates in thermodynamics and is always associated with volume. The actual pressure at a given location is called absolute pressure and is measured relative to the pressure (Absolute Vacuum) where the absolute pressure is equal to zero. Most pressure gauges measure pressure difference, as the zero point is considered to be atmospheric pressure, so they measure the difference between absolute pressure and local atmospheric pressure, this difference is called measured pressure and the pressure less than atmospheric pressure is called vacuum pressure and is measured by vacuum gauges, which measure the difference between atmospheric pressure and absolute pressure. Atmospheric pressure: Atmospheric pressure is the force exerted by air above a surface while gravity pulls it towards the ground, as the air contains a weight that presses on every surface it touches, and this pressure is what is known as atmospheric pressure or air pressure.

Blood Pressure:

It is the number that expresses the pressure that blood exerts on the arteries. The body, and to understand this more clearly, it is worth stating that the heart is responsible for pumping blood filled with oxygen and nutrients to the various tissues of the body, from the left side of the heart through the arteries, which creates pressure on the arteries, which is expressed as blood pressure. In fact, blood pressure reaches its peak when the heart muscle contracts at the moment the heart pumps blood, and the resulting blood pressure is known as systole, while blood pressure reaches its lowest levels when it relaxes and rests between contractions in order to refill it with blood, and is then known as diastole. From the context of what was mentioned, we conclude that pressure is very important for delivering oxygen and nutrients to the various tissues of the body, and blood pressure is also important for delivering and transporting white blood cells and antibodies important for immunity, as well as for transporting some hormones such as insulin. On the other hand, the blood nourished with oxygen when it reaches the cells. And provides it with the necessary nutrients, it is able to capture carbon dioxide and other compounds resulting from the metabolic processes that occur in the cell, including toxins that the body excretes through the liver and kidneys.

Research objective:

The current research aims to identify atmospheric pressure and blood pressure and how to measure them and the difference between them. The importance of the research also depends on the importance of the problem being studied, its scientific value, and what can be achieved in terms of results that can be used and facts that can be relied upon, in addition to what the research can achieve for science, the researcher and the readers of the research from a scientific point of view, as well as what it achieves in terms of benefit to society from a practical and applied point of view.

The importance of this research is embodied in the following:

1. Identify atmospheric pressure and blood pressure.
2. Know how to measure pressure.
3. Identify some of the devices used in the process of measuring pressure.

Blood pressure:

is the force of blood pushing against the walls of the blood vessels through which it travels while nourishing all the tissues and organs of the body in what is known as blood circulation. Blood circulation begins with

the contraction of the heart muscle to forcefully push all its contents of blood, which in turn moves from the heart to the aorta, the largest artery in the human body, and from there to the rest of the arteries of the body. Then the heart expands to allow it to be filled with a new amount of blood to contract again, pushing a new charge to the aorta again, and so on. Medical statistics show the great importance of maintaining blood pressure so that it is on average 75-115 mm Hg, and that increasing it above this limit leads to stress on the heart and kidneys, and its increase may lead to stroke or early infertility in men. The aorta is characterized by flexibility. When blood coming from the heart rushes, it creates high pressure on the walls of the artery, causing it to expand laterally. During cardiac relaxation, the artery regains its normal position, pressing on the blood it contains, causing it to rush, and thus the blood continues to flow during relaxation. Blood pressure during heart contraction is called systolic pressure, and during relaxation it is called diastolic pressure. Systolic pressure is always higher in value than diastolic pressure. When measuring blood pressure, the reading is written as a fraction, for example 80/120, where the systolic pressure value is the highest and the diastolic value is the lowest. Meteorologist Jennifer Fanous explained that when atmospheric pressure drops, blood pressure automatically drops, and it also causes dizziness for some people in addition to blurred vision. Normal human pressure Blood pressure is one of the important vital indicators of human life, as previously mentioned, blood pressure is responsible for delivering oxygen and nutrients from the arteries through the circulatory system to the various tissues and organs of the body. As for blood pressure readings; It is worth noting that the reading is considered normal if the systolic blood pressure is between 90 and 120 mm Hg, and the diastolic blood pressure is between 60 and 80 mm Hg. High blood pressure: What is closely related to talking about blood pressure is what is known as high blood pressure, which is a condition that represents high blood pressure for a long period of time in a way that increases the chance of suffering from some health problems, such as heart disease, if the condition is not controlled properly. High blood pressure is likely if the blood pressure reading is 130/80 mm Hg or more. Unfortunately, blood pressure may be high for several years without the person noticing it, because this disease is usually not accompanied by symptoms, but it is easy to diagnose and investigate through periodic visits to the doctor. It is worth noting that it is very important to adhere to the instructions of the specialist doctor and the plan he sets to control high blood pressure to avoid potential complications such as clots and others. In the context of talking about high blood pressure, it is worth noting that this health problem has two types, primary and secondary hypertension, and the following is a statement of each of them:

Primary hypertension: This is the most common type, and usually develops over several years, and the chance of developing it increases with age. Secondary hypertension: It results from taking a certain medication or contracting a certain disease or health problem, and treating the problem that caused it and stopping taking the medication that caused it is also sufficient to return blood pressure to what it was before.

2-2 Low blood pressure: Low blood pressure or low blood pressure (: Hypotensio) expresses the condition in which the pressure is lower than normal or lower than expected, taking into account the surrounding environmental factors. Some have shown that blood pressure is considered low if it is less than 90/60 mm Hg, but it is considered very normal if this pressure does not cause symptoms or signs, and does not cause problems for the person concerned, while low blood pressure accompanied by symptoms requires seeing a doctor to obtain appropriate treatment. Among the symptoms that may accompany low blood pressure are: feeling heavy in the head, feeling tired, weak and confused, and it may also cause blurred vision, nausea, pain in the neck and back, and heart palpitations. ¹³ Low blood pressure can be temporary, and it can be chronic in other cases. In fact, there are types of low blood pressure, some of which are common in certain categories of people. The following is a statement of the most important of these types in some detail.

Orthostatic hypotension: People with this type of low blood pressure feel dizzy or faint when changing position suddenly, including standing. Pregnant women and the elderly are the most affected.

Postprandial hypotension: People with this type feel dizzy or faint after eating due to a sudden drop in blood pressure. The elderly are the most affected.

Neurally mediated hypotension: People with this type feel dizzy,

nauseous, and faint after exercising or standing for a long period of time. To learn more about low blood pressure, you can read the following article: (Low blood pressure, symptoms, and treatment).

Orthostatic hypotension:

People with this type of low blood pressure feel dizzy or may faint when changing position suddenly, including standing, and the most affected groups are pregnant women and the elderly.

Postprandial hypotension:

People with this type feel dizzy or faint after eating due to a sudden drop in blood pressure, and the most affected groups are the elderly. **Neurally mediated hypotension:** People with this type feel dizzy, nauseous and faint after exercising or standing for a long period of time. **How to measure blood pressure** Regularly measuring blood pressure helps diagnose health problems early, as measuring blood pressure is the only way to diagnose high blood pressure. In fact, high blood pressure does not cause any symptoms or signs that help those affected know about it. Blood pressure may be measured at the doctor, in the pharmacy, or at home. A number of medical devices are usually used when measuring blood pressure manually, including: a stethoscope, an inflatable rubber cuff with a squeezable balloon, and a blood pressure monitor. The healthcare provider wraps the rubber cuff around the patient's arm, presses the squeezable balloon until the cuff inflates, then allows the air to be emptied from the cuff while listening to the heartbeat using a stethoscope and noting the reading when the heartbeat is heard for the first time, which is known as systolic blood pressure, and continuing to listen to the heartbeat and noting the reading when the heartbeat stops, which is known as diastolic blood pressure. Some people may measure blood pressure using digital or automated blood pressure devices in which the stethoscope is dispensed with, as these devices are considered more accurate and easier to use. Use, and the methods of operating these devices may differ, so the correct instructions for operating and using them must be followed.

The importance of measuring blood pressure:

The importance of measuring blood pressure lies in avoiding complications resulting from any defect, whether an increase or decrease in the blood pressure measurement, as when it rises, this means that the heart faces great resistance to pumping blood to the body's arteries, which causes heart failure in the long term, which in turn leads to death. High blood pressure also leads to stroke or kidney failure, if the disease is not treated at its beginning with appropriate medical drugs. Low blood pressure also suggests that the amount of blood reaching the body's organs is not reaching sufficiently or quickly enough, which means a decrease in the arrival of oxygen and food to the body's tissues, which harms them, causing partial or complete destruction, especially the brain, which is the first organ to be affected, causing a person to feel bouts of fatigue and general weakness, which may be followed by the individual losing consciousness. In general, low blood pressure is considered a "disease" if it has symptoms such as dizziness and persistent general weakness.

Measuring blood pressure

Blood pressure is measured in a unit called millimeters of mercury in a relaxed state (i.e. when the person is still and at rest). We find that the normal measurement of systolic blood pressure for an average adult ranges between 90 and 140 mm Hg, while diastolic ranges between 60 and 90 mm Hg. That is, the average is 120 mm Hg systolic and 80 mm Hg diastolic, and it reads 80/120 mm Hg, while the public calls it 120 over 80 or 120 over 80 mm Hg. To measure blood pressure, an electronic device is used at home or a manual device in the doctor's clinic, which is known as a mercury blood pressure monitor, and it is the most accurate.

Table (1)

تصنيف ضغط الدم في البالغين (بالمليمتر زئبق)		
عمود ضغط الدم	عمود الانقباضي	عمود الانبساطي
مستوى طبيعي	أقل من ١٢٠	أقل من ٨٠
مستوى ما قبل المرضي	120-139	80-89
المرحلة الأولى من فرط ضغط دموي متوسط الشدة	140-159	90-99
المرحلة الثانية من فرط ضغط دموي شديد	أكثر من ١٦٠	أكثر من ١٠٠

What is a blood pressure device:

Sphygmomanometers is a Greek term meaning blood pressure gauge. The term comes from the Greek word "pulse" which means "pulse" and "manometer" which means meter pressure. It is a means used to assess blood pressure and express the extent of the force with which blood affects the arteries.

Components of a blood pressure device:

Figure (1) Components of a blood pressure device:

1. A wrist cuff or a wide elastic band that can be filled with air.
2. A rubber inflator that can pump air into the cuff.
3. A scale or a glass tube containing mercury.
4. A stethoscope.

Measurement process:

To measure blood pressure, a cuff is wrapped around the patient's arm. A stethoscope is placed on the arteries just below the cuff. Blood pulsations can be heard in the arteries. Air is pumped into the cuff, which compresses the arteries. This stops blood flow, and the pulsations cannot be heard. Then the air is slowly emptied from the cuff. When the cuff pressure becomes less than the blood pressure, blood flow resumes. The pressure at which blood flow begins is called systolic pressure, which represents blood pressure when the heart contracts. This pressure is determined by reading the gauge or glass tube containing mercury. As the air comes out of the cuff, the sounds become dull. The pressure at this point is called diastolic pressure, which represents blood pressure when the heart relaxes.

Types of Blood Pressure Measuring Devices:

Blood Pressure There are three types of blood pressure measuring devices:

- Digital devices, where the air is pumped manually, which can be used in places where there is noise where it is not necessary to listen to the pulse accurately with a stethoscope.
- Portable digital devices, which are less accurate in measurement. They are used to measure blood pressure on the finger or wrist and the reading is displayed on a screen showing the difference between systolic and diastolic pressures, heart rate and pulse.
- Manual mercury devices, which must be used by trained people. When using them, there must be no noise to accurately start hearing the pulse sound. Manual blood pressure gauges are used with a stethoscope. The most common manual devices include mercury blood pressure gauges. The mercury device is considered the gold standard in measuring blood pressure compared to other types, and calibration errors do not occur very often. It is very accurate and reliable. On the other hand, aneroid devices are used, but they require regular calibration checks, which is unlike mercury pressure measurement. Aneroid blood pressure gauges are less expensive and are considered safer than mercury-containing devices. Digital blood pressure gauges are electronic devices that use vibration measurements and electronic calculations to measure blood pressure. These devices are easy to operate even for a person without training.

Choosing the right device:

It is best to choose a device that measures blood pressure in the upper arm and not on the wrist or finger. Make sure that the device is listed as “clinically validated.” Validation means that the device has undergone a series of tests to ensure its accuracy and efficiency. Get one with the right size wrist, an incorrectly sized cuff can give you incorrect readings. Having a blood pressure device at home will help you monitor your blood pressure and has its benefits. First, you will be able to track your blood pressure regularly, which can help determine whether the medications you are taking are affecting your blood pressure or not.

Pressure measuring devices

Atmospheric pressure measuring devices vary as follows: Mercury Barometer: The mercury barometer is one of the oldest types of atmospheric pressure measuring devices and was invented by the Italian physicist Evangelista Torricelli in 1643. His experiments began with a tube filled with water, but due to the light weight of water, a very long tube had to be used to measure the heavier atmospheric pressure. His water barometer was more than ten meters long and longer than his house, which raised suspicion among Torricelli's neighbors who believed that he was practicing witchcraft. Therefore, he thought of replacing water with mercury to make a smaller barometer because the weight of mercury is fourteen times that of water. The mercury barometer consists of a glass tube with a closed mouth and an open base, and at the base is a shallow circular dish filled with mercury, which changes with changes in atmospheric pressure. When

the atmospheric pressure rises, the mercury rises to the top of the tube, and the measurement can be known by reading the number or meter to which the mercury rises. Aneroid Barometer: In 1844, the French scientist Lucien Vidi invented the aneroid barometer, which gradually replaced the mercury barometer because it was less expensive and easier to use and transport. This device consists of a closed metal layer that contracts or expands according to the surrounding atmospheric pressure, and mechanical instruments measure the degree of contraction or expansion of this layer. Digital Barometers: Modern digital barometers display more complex weather data with greater accuracy and speed than before. Many of them display current readings and readings for an hour, three, six or twelve hours ago, as well as data such as wind and humidity. Atmospheric pressure can be expressed in several units of measurement that differ slightly in their values, including millimeters of mercury, which is equivalent to 760 millimeters of mercury, or pounds per square inch (abbreviated in English as psi), which is equivalent to 14.70, or dynes per square centimeter, which is equivalent to $1,013.25 \times 10^3$, or millibars, which is equivalent to 1,013.25, or kilopascals, which is equivalent to 101.325.

The effect of altitude on humans:

The atmospheric pressure decreases with height above the Earth's surface, and thus the oxygen in the atmosphere decreases, which has an effect on living organisms that breathe air and need oxygen to breathe. The effect of altitude on humans is as follows:

- Altitude of 2400 meters: This is equivalent to the pressure inside passenger planes, and has no effect
- Altitude of 2500 meters: Some sensitive people start to feel dizzy.
- Altitude of 3500 meters: About a third of people who are not used to this feel dizzy and tired.
- Altitude of 4000 meters: 95% of those who are not used to it feel dizzy and tired.
- Altitude of 5500 meters: Some people can live at this altitude. The amount of oxygen at this altitude is about half of its amount at sea level.
- Altitude of 7500 meters: Here begins the deadly zone: Mountain climbers cannot stay at this altitude for more than a day without oxygen tubes.
- 8848 meters high: The highest point on Earth, Mount Everest, cannot survive at that height without oxygen tubes.
- 12192 meters high: The average flight altitude for commercial aircraft. Here, the cabin is supplied with compressed air from outside, with its temperature controlled.

2-13 Atmospheric pressure measuring device:

1. Manometer:

Figure (2) (a, b) (representing the manometer)

Device components:

A tube in the shape of B filled with a liquid (mercury, water or oil).

Working mechanism: -

One end of the manometer is connected to the fluid whose pressure is to be measured. The change in pressure causes a difference in height between the legs of the manometer. According to the pressure difference in the equation

$$P^A - P = \rho h g \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

Advantages of the manometer

- It cannot be calibrated by any other standard.
- It is suitable for long periods of use without distortion (and long life).
- It is simple and less expensive than others.

Disadvantages of the manometer

- 1 It cannot be used to measure high pressures.
- 2 Some liquids have a concave surface, which leads to an error in measurement.
- 3 The surface tension of liquids in capillary tubes (with a diameter of less than 15 mm) leads to incorrect measurement.
- 4 One of the biggest disadvantages is that it cannot be used to measure changing pressures because it is slow to respond.

Important points to consider in the manometer

1. The diameter of the tube should not be less than 15 mm.
- 2 Ensure that the tube connecting the manometer to the tank or tube in which the pressure of the liquid inside is to be measured is free of bubbles.
3. It is preferable to use the inclined manometer in cases of very low pressures, because it can read the slight change in pressure because the increase in the level.
4. The height of the barrier appears clearly in the inclined tube.

Figure (4) Inclined manometer

Mercury barometer

Figure (5) Mercury barometer

Components

1 basin filled with mercury.

2 tube one meter long closed at one end. *اللية العمل*

The tube is placed vertically in the mercury basin with its closed end facing up and the open end facing down so that the tube is partially submerged in the mercury. When the atmospheric pressure affects the surface of the mercury in the basin, this leads to a decrease in the mercury level in the basin and its rise inside the tube. The amount of pressure is calculated from the equation

$$P = hgp \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Macleod scale

Figure (6) Macleod scale

- It is used to measure very low pressures.
- The gas whose pressure is to be measured must meet Boyle's Law.

$$P1v1 = P2v2 \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Components

A mercury tank immersed in a piston, the tank is connected to a reference column and a bulb at the cutoff point. The reference column is connected to a capillary tube at a point called a reference with a reference point called the zero point. There is a graduated tube at the top of the bulb.

Mechanism of operation

There are two states of the scale: -

First state: When the piston is not under the influence of force, when the tube to be measured is connected to the reference column, the gas fills the reference capillary tube, the reference column, the bulb and the graduated tube. The four parts are filled with gas up to the point called the cutoff point. The part below the cutoff point is filled with mercury up to the tank.

The second case: When an external force begins to affect the piston, when an external force affects the piston, the piston presses the mercury downwards, so the mercury rises upwards on the other side of the scale. As the force continues to affect, the mercury continues to rise until it reaches the cutoff point. As the mercury continues to rise, the gas whose pressure is to be measured is confined in the graduated tube until the mercury reaches the zero-reference point, and then v_1 and p_2 is calculated according to the following equations:

$$V_1 = v + ahc \dots \dots \dots (5)$$

V: represents the volume of the bulb.

a: represents the cross-sectional area of the graduated tube.

hc: represents the height of the graduated tube.

V1: represents the volume of the gas before compression.

Calibration

It is comparing the devices used with internationally agreed standard devices in terms of accuracy and stored under specific environmental conditions. Most of the calibration operations carried out in student laboratories are comparison operations with devices of known accuracy, the aim of which is to know the accuracy of the measurement.

Measurement

Finding the amount of a physical quantity or physical variable or estimating a condition using an appropriate device or tool. If the device used is an internationally agreed standard device, the measurement process is considered a calibration process and the measured quantity is then a standard quantity. However, if the device is not standard, the measurement process is a comparison with the standard quantity and a device that has been calibrated before may be used for this.

Concepts used in the measurement process:

1. Accuracy (precision) The accuracy of the device is its ability to give a reading that is closest to the true "standard" reading. The closer the device gives a reading to the actual "standard" amount of the measured quantity, the more accurate the device is. Accuracy is a measure of the degree of error in the final measured result. The accuracy of the device can be determined by giving the extent of the error that the device gives when measuring a certain range of the measured quantity. For example: A thermometer described as giving an error of $\pm 5.0^\circ\text{C}$ in the range (50°C to 100°C) can be said to have an accuracy of 5.0°C in this range.

2. Accuracy is the ability of the device to give the same reading when the measurement process is repeated with the same device. The more accurate the device is, the closer the readings it gives for the same quantity when the measurement process is repeated will be to each other.

3. The response of the device is the amount of displacement that can be caused by the smallest amount of the measured quantity that is readable. 4. The measurement error is the difference between the amount of the measured quantity and the actual "standard" amount of the quantity.

Types of measurement errors

➤ Total error

Error Human errors in reading and using this type of device and in recording and calculating measurement results. These errors cannot be processed mathematically, but they must be avoided with care and attention and knowledge of taking correct readings and recording them through practice and exercise. Under all circumstances, one should not be satisfied with taking one reading, but rather take at least three different readings for the same quantity under different conditions.

➤ Monotonous errors

They are usually divided into two groups:

1. Device errors that occur due to device defects. These are errors inherent in measuring devices due to moving mechanical devices that are affected by friction, which results in what is known as a friction error, or a twist occurs in the "spring" connected to the parts of the cycles, or an irregularity in the extension of the spring as a result of misuse of the device, such as passing a current higher than the permissible one. These defects lead to errors in the reading known as distortion errors. There are also errors that occur as a result of the age of the device.

2. Environmental errors that occur due to the influence of the environment surrounding the devices

These are errors of external influences such as thermal effects, the effect of humidity, atmospheric pressure, or electrical and magnetic fields on the devices. These errors can be eliminated by taking the necessary precautions and treating the conditions surrounding the devices before using them.

3. Random errors

The causes of these errors are unknown and they always exist even after eliminating all the monotonous errors. Although random errors in carefully planned experiments are usually small, they are of great importance when the required accuracy is high.

Calculations:

1. Comparison between a laboratory-made mercury device and an electronic device manufactured by a manufacturing company

Table (2) Readings

رقم القراءة	الجهاز المصنع		الجهاز الإلكتروني		نسبة التغير في الضغط الانبساطي mmhg	التغير في الضغط الانقباضي mmhg	نسبة التغير في الضغط الانقباضي %	التغير في الضغط الانبساطي mmhg	نسبة التغير في الضغط الانقباضي %
	الضغط الانبساطي mmhg	الضغط الانقباضي mmhg	الضغط الانبساطي mmhg	الضغط الانقباضي mmhg					
1	59	89	67	101	-11.9	-8	-11.9	-12	-11.9
2	65	100	78	117	-16.7	-13	-14.5	-17	-16.7
3	70	127	76	118	-7.9	-6	7.6	9	-7.9
4	70	105	82	109	-14.6	-12	-3.7	-4	-14.6
5	75	110	82	111	-8.5	-7	-0.9	-1	-8.5
6	65	95	93	113	-30.1	-28	-15.9	-18	-30.1
7	60	100	81	113	-25.9	-21	-11.5	-13	-25.9
8	75	120	108	145	-30.6	-33	-17.2	-25	-30.6
9	70	100	77	124	-9.1	-7	-19.4	-24	-9.1
10	70	92	74	103	-5.4	-4	-10.7	-11	-5.4
11	65	90	74	114	-12.2	-9	-21.1	-24	-12.2
12	70	105	79	117	-11.4	-9	-10.3	-12	-11.4
13	55	90	74	103	-25.7	-19	-12.6	-13	-25.7
14	80	100	92	121	-13.0	-12	-17.4	-21	-13.0
15	76	128	92	128	-17.4	-16	0.0	0	-17.4
16	70	120	96	143	-27.1	-26	-16.1	-23	-27.1
17	70	115	79	117	-11.4	-9	-1.7	-2	-11.4
18	50	110	82	116	-39.0	-32	-5.2	-6	-39.0
19	50	100	96	119	-47.9	-46	-16.0	-19	-47.9
20	55	100	79	103	-30.4	-24	-2.9	-3	-30.4

Table (3)

11.3	الانحراف المعياري للضغط الانبساطي
9.6	الانحراف المعياري للضغط الانقباضي

Comparison between a laboratory-made mercury device and an electronic device manufactured by a manufacturing company.

Conclusion:

- In this research, we have come to know that atmospheric pressure is the force exerted by air above the surface, while blood pressure is the force of blood pushing against the walls of blood vessels.
- As well as the difference between measuring devices in the measurement process, as well as the difference between manual devices and those manufactured by the factory.
- As well as the difference in readings of electronic devices from mercury.

- It was found that atmospheric pressure does not differ from blood pressure, as her words are related to the other, as meteorologist Jennifer Fanous explained that when atmospheric pressure decreases, blood pressure automatically decreases.
- Atmospheric pressure is absolute pressure.
- Gauge pressure is the pressure above atmospheric pressure. Therefore, it is relative pressure.
- Atmospheric pressure at sea level is constant.

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